

MEDIATIZED DISCOURSES ON EUROPEANIZATION AND THEIR REPRESENTATIONS IN PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS

Policy Brief: Mediatized representations and public perceptions of Europeanization – key challenges and opportunities for the future of the European project

The power of mediatized discourses on Europeanization

Media framing of the European Union plays a central role in constructing public perceptions of the European project and attitudes towards EU enlargement. MEDIATIZED EU research shows how media discourses can be created to foster or hamper the European project, focusing on the elite-media-public triangle. The ongoing mediatization of political discourses has a direct impact on the representations of the EU in elite debates and on how these resonate with public perceptions of Europeanization, in turn influencing media coverage and public opinion of the present and future of the EU.

Core findings

1) Pragmatic factors drive the dominant pro-European consensus across country contexts because pragmatic benefits of EU membership, such as freedom of movement or greater educational opportunities, are evident, easily communicated and grasped by the public.

2) Identitarian discourses are primarily used by Euroskeptical elites and outlets and fueled by disinformation and politically polarizing rhetoric. However, identity concerns can also contribute to pro-European views, especially

when they deal with issues of shared European values or belonging to a European community.

3) Despite the evident dominance of pro-European attitudes among all major interest groups, our research suggests that Euroskeptical ideas can easily gain support in certain segments of society. Such skepticism arises when the EU is instrumentalized and represented as interfering in national matters

Key Messages

- There is an urgent need to **enhance citizens' 'EU literacy'** through direct engagement and by facilitating higher-quality coverage of EU affairs by independent media outlets featuring a diversity of voices.
- Combatting misrepresentations of the EU (including FIMI) requires a **more forward-thinking strategy** encompassing technical, legal and diplomatic measures and cross-sectoral collaboration frameworks.
- Member States should prioritize **civil society engagement with EU institutions**, widening civic participation in EU decision-making processes, mediatized debates, and educational programs.

or threatening national sovereignty, aggravating the existing divisions within societies.

4) A key factor in making the public more susceptible to misrepresentations and more prone to misperceptions is the relatively low level of knowledge about EU affairs. This lack of 'EU literacy' is exacerbated by the general rise of social polarization, the impact of major geopolitical crises and conflicts affecting the continent, diminished trust in institutions and independent media. These provide opportunities for both internal and external actors to exploit the public fears and ignorance and to foment skeptical and even hostile views on EU unity, policies and initiatives.

5) In the rapidly digitizing media landscape, dominated by large social media platforms, low EU literacy is supplemented by lacking digital skills among key segments of the public, further increasing the risk of misinformation targeting EU values and solidarity and easier manipulation of public opinion through divisive discourses.

Implications for EU policy and practice

Our research provides policymakers with up-to-date insights on the media representations of the European project, as well as the interconnections between elite discourses, EU framing and public perceptions, enabling them to develop informed strategies for tackling threats to EU values, Euroskeptic attitudes and harmful anti-EU narratives. Our insights help develop effective strategies for responding to Euroskeptic discourses and anti-EU misinformation and inform interventions and literacy strategies to improve public awareness of the EU. Our research moves scholarly and policymaking expertise beyond the state of the art and is already contributing useful insights across national contexts, in light of the updated EU strategic priorities in areas of democracy promotion, media freedom and EU enlargement. Our insights are particularly timely as the EU is undergoing a radical rethinking of political and security architectures

in the face of Russian aggression in Ukraine; as new countries engage in accession negotiations and obtain EU candidate status; and as Member States debate the extent of the EU's normative power and the ongoing rule of law backsliding and disinformation threats within the EU.

Policy recommendations:

- **Further enhance citizen media literacy and design more robust strategies for protecting citizen agency and rights online.** The public are increasingly using digital media channels to obtain news and information yet are concerned about media manipulation and restrictions on political debate online. This requires a unified EU approach that is more participatory, focuses on enhancing citizen media literacy and is based on best practices from across the EU. Building on relevant European directives and regulatory acts, Member States should prioritize the protection of fundamental rights online and seek to enhance civic agency and individual security, giving citizens greater control over their data, news feeds and discursive spaces online.
- **Support greater citizen engagement with EU institutions through new opportunities for participation.** Fostering more active engagement in EU-related affairs and debates among citizens is one of the most pressing issues for the EU. Media coverage should also focus on public interest aspects and explanatory reporting about opportunities for citizen participation in EU affairs in practical ways. Policymakers should support grassroots, civil society and community contributions to policymaking and political initiatives, as well as provide opportunities for training and skills exchange to promote community leadership initiatives and cross-EU collaborations.
- **Devise a more forward-thinking strategy to counter disinformation and strengthen societal resilience.** The use of disinformation in political disputes and

campaigns, resulting in growing political polarization and mistrust in public institutions, should be the focus of attention in Europe's efforts to tackle these issues. The EU should build on existing mechanisms and institutional frameworks regulating digital media, and Member State participation in the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation, to devise a more forward-thinking strategy to counter disinformation. This should include independent media and digital platforms to ensure accountability and best practice adoption but should also actively involve non-governmental organizations and community groups to adapt literacy and counter disinformation initiatives to their needs.

- **Promote a free and independent media environment and quality EU affairs reporting across the EU and in its neighborhood.** The EU needs to push for institutional and legal reforms at the Member State level to promote transparency in media ownership, sustainable media freedom and diversity across national contexts. The EU should also develop cross-border cooperation and allocate funding to facilitate higher-quality coverage of EU affairs by independent media outlets featuring a diversity of voices to mitigate political bias and political parallelism, as well as guard against autocratic media capture and external interference in media spaces.

- **Enable joined-up strategy development and policymaking across key EU strategic priorities.**¹ Our insights and recommendations highlight the importance of making policy that connects European security and defense; EU-wide social solidarity; promoting democracy as a core European value; European enlargement and strengthened European institutions; and building stronger, forward-looking, Europe on the global stage. From key insights for the development of the European Democracy Shield to nurturing independent journalism and civil society resilience as part of the European

Democracy Action Plan and combatting disinformation and foreign interference threats in the EU, our research findings and policy recommendations inform the EU's strategic priorities as a global protector of democracy and human rights and as a champion of the European way of life.

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Website: mediatized.eu

Email: contact@mediatized.eu

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¹ https://european-union.europa.eu/priorities-and-actions/eu-priorities/european-union-priorities-2024-2029_en